

OPEN SCIENCE AND RESEARCHER EVALUATION

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UNIVERSIDADE DO ALGARVE

UAlg events for International Open Access Week

A Universidade do Algarve, através do **UAlg ODC - Centro de Dados Abertos de Investigação** e da **Biblioteca**, celebra a **Semana Internacional do Acesso Aberto**.

O tema deste ano, "**A quem pertence o nosso conhecimento?**", desafia-nos a defender a abertura e a equidade na produção e disseminação científica.

Participe nas nossas sessões de formação, maioritariamente *online*, para fortalecer as suas competências em Ciência Aberta.

CENTRO DE DADOS ABERTOS DE INVESTIGAÇÃO DA UNIVERSIDADE DO ALGARVE

20 OUT | SEG

10h30-12h30

Zotero, Gestor Bibliográfico e de PDF's e outras ferramentas de revisão da literatura

Online Comunidade académica

Inscrição em: <https://tinyurl.com/4cewieam>

21 OUT | TER

11h30-13h00

Open Science and Researcher Evaluation

Presencial - Biblioteca Gambelas Docentes, investigadores

Inscrição: Membros da UAlg <https://tinyurl.com/bddj2eud>
Externos: cienciaaberta@ualg.pt

22 OUT | QUA

11h30-12h30

Onde publicar com a nova política da FCT: revistas híbridas, GOA ou diamante

Online Docentes, investigadores e estudantes de mestrado e doutoramento Inscrição: Membros da UAlg <https://tinyurl.com/ydjk32yc>
Externos: cienciaaberta@ualg.pt

23 OUT | QUI

11h00-13h00

Rumo a uma cultura de dados abertos: da organização à partilha apoiada no PGD

Online Docentes, investigadores e estudantes de mestrado e doutoramento Inscrição: Membros da UAlg <https://tinyurl.com/3amu7n2b>
Externos: cienciaaberta@ualg.pt

24 OUT | SEX

11h30-12h30

Como Avaliar a Fiabilidade das Publicações Científicas

Online Comunidade académica

Inscrição: Membros da UAlg <https://tinyurl.com/4rt2umda>
Externos: cienciaaberta@ualg.pt

<https://projeto.rcaap.pt/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/UAlg-Semana-OAW2025.pdf>

Iniciativa institucional - UAlg

Centro de Dados Abertos da UAlg (UAlg-ODC) e Ciência Aberta (CA)

A UAlg compromete-se com a ciência aberta e com as alterações nas práticas científicas e de gestão, que ela envolve, e como tal é assinante do Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment.

<https://www.ualg.pt/cienciaaberta>

PLANNIG

**What is Open
Science (OS)?**

**OS and
Evaluation:
National Context**

**Research
Traditional
Evaluation**

**Concrete
Initiatives**

**OS and Evaluation:
International Context**

Open Peer Review

Limitations of «Traditional» Evaluation Criteria: The Impact Factor (IF)

- Impact Factor (IF): An indicator that indirectly estimates the visibility of a scientific journal ;
- The impact factor of a journal is the average number of citations of articles in the journal relative to the number of articles published by the journal. It is commonly calculated over two years.

Produced by Clarivate Analytics in the Journal Citation Reports.

The impact factor of a journal for year **N** is calculated using the following ratio:

$$IF (N) = A/B$$

Where: A = number of paper cited in the previous two years

B = number of citable publications in the journal in the previous 2 years

Limitations of «Traditional» Evaluation Criteria: The Impact Factor (IF)

✓ Largely favors English-language articles.

✓ Intended for the journal, not the article or author

✓ Index can be manipulated depending on the types of articles published (state of the art + cited)

✓ Articles published in a high-impact journal do not all receive a large number of citations; some articles may not receive any at all.

✓ Potentially encourages bad practices: self-citation, fragmentation of results.

2 Calculation over two years not necessarily suitable for all disciplines

Limitations of «Traditional» Evaluation

Criteria: h-index

h-index

- An author's h-index is equal to the highest number h of their publications that have received at least h citations each.
- Also depends on the sources used to calculate it.
- Increases automatically with the « researcher's academic age ».
- Depends largely on the citation habits of the discipline.
- Sensitive to self-citation.

Limitations of «Traditional» Evaluation

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An author's **h-index** is equal to the highest number h of their publications that have received at least h citations each.

Alternative to «Traditional» Evaluation Criteria: the Altmetrics

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Mentioned by

Citations

Readers on

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Open Science (OS): Definition

- ➔ **Open Data**
- ➔ **Open Source**
- ➔ **Open Access**
- ➔ **Open Methodology**
- ➔ **Open Peer Review**
- ➔ **Open Educational Resources**

**Open Science (OS):
Definition**

Open science is the unhindered dissemination of research publications and data. It builds on the opportunities presented by the digital revolution.

Open science is the practice of science that enables collaboration and contribution with others, where research data, lab notes, and other research processes are freely available, under conditions that allow for the reuse, redistribution, and reproduction of the research, as well as its underlying data and methods.

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CHALLENGES

ACADEMIC CHALLENGES

POLITICAL CHALLENGES

ECONOMIC ISSUES

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San Francisco
Statement
On
Research
Assessment
(2012)

REIMAGINING RESEARCH ASSESSMENT: THE DORA DECLARATION

Focusing on Value, Not Venue

URGENT NEED TO IMPROVE METHODS

- End Journal-Based Indicators (Impact Factor)
- Evaluate Intrinsic Research Value
- Leverage Online Publishing (Flexible Formats, New Metrics)

2012: Developed at ASCB Mtg.
Global Initiative

DORA PRINCIPLES

Consider All Outputs
(Data, Software, etc.)

Concerned Entities: Funding Agencies, Institutions, Journals, Researchers

Leiden principles (2015)

The 10 principles of the Leiden Manifesto for research metrics

(Hicks et al., 2015)

AMSTERDAM CALL FOR ACTION (2016)

Open Science in Europe

1. FULL OPEN ACCESS
for all
scientific publications

2. OPTIMAL REUSE OF RESEARCH DATA
(Fundamentally New Approach)

New systems for assessing,
promoting, and evaluating research

Alignment of policies and
exchange on best practices

EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD (EOSC) 2018 INITIATIVE

An open, trusted, integrated, multi-disciplinary environment for researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens

FAIR PRINCIPLES

GOALS

Support for Open Science &
Connecting Infrastructures

CALL OF PARIS (2022)

EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE DAYS

- ❖ **REAFFIRM** alignment of evaluation with recognition
- ❖ **EVALUATE** merits & impacts, not just publications, promoting qualitative peer-review
- ❖ **FORM COALITION** for research evaluation reform

CoARA (2022)

Coalition Advancing Research Assessment

- ❖ **GLOBAL COALITION** to reform research assessment
- ❖ **VISION:** Recognize diverse outputs & impacts, prioritizing qualitative judgement
- ❖ **MISSION:** Drive systemic reform through collaboration & learning
- ❖ **FORM COALITION** for research collaboration & learn

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Open Access carried out by the universities, which have taken different initiatives to expand access to research information.

Universidade do Minho

The 1st Portuguese Open Access initiatives from UMinho with the creation of RepositóriUM (October 2003), and the subsequent definition of a pioneering self-archiving policy (January 2005).

RCAAP

In 2008, the RCAAP (Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal = Portugal Open Access Science Repository) initiative was established.

At the national level, we have more than 50 institutional repositories aggregated in RCAAP, and 27 hosted in RCAAP infrastructure;

- Academic press and scientific journals are expanding within research institutions and more recently, the [PubIn project](#), developed by the University of Minho (UMinho) in collaboration with (FCT/FCCN), with the purpose of addressing the current situation of scientific publishing in Portugal;
- Currently, we have more than 200 journals aggregated in RCAAP and 30 journals hosted in the same service.
- At the national level, there are several institutional mandates, currently, we have 29 ([ROARMAP](#)).

When researchers apply for funding or when research units are evaluated, open science contributions are increasingly considered.

These include:

Open Access to Publications

Researchers must make publications resulting from FCT-funded projects openly available. Depositing in institutional or national repositories is required.

Research Data Management (RDM) & FAIR Data

Since 2022, FCT requires Data Management Plans (DMPs) for funded projects. Compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles is encouraged and assessed.

Software and Other Outputs

Contributions such as open-source software, datasets, preprints, and protocols are recognized as valid research outputs.

EVALUATION

Engagement & Science Communication

Open knowledge dissemination, public engagement, and citizen science initiatives can strengthen evaluation, especially under societal impact criteria.

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The issue of Open Peer Review

As opposed to the traditional single-blind or double-blind review process, open peer review (OPR) allows the process to be opened to varying degrees:

The issue of Open Peer Review

**Open
interaction**

**Reciprocal discussions
between parties.**

**Open pre-
review
manuscripts**

**Manuscripts immediately
available before formal
peer review.**

**Open final-
version
commenting**

**Review or commenting on
final “version of record”
publications.**

**Open
platforms**

**Review facilitated entity
other than the venue of
publication.**

The (Potential) Benefits of Open Peer Review

Benefits

- Transparency: removal of anonymity, higher quality reports
- Speed if open to the community, larger pool of reviewers
- Trust: review does not depend on just one or two anonymous reviewers
- Consistency: reasons for rejection or acceptance explained in the report
- Contextualization: clarification of the methodology and research process
- Motivation: possibility of giving credit to reviewers and promoting this scientific activity in researcher evaluations

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Narrative CV

This type of CV should enable researchers to show their skills and experience rather than simply listing funding and publications.

Example of a narrative CV provided by FCT.

In this CV, researchers are asked to present their career in four areas:

- Their contribution to the development of knowledge in their field
- Their contribution to the development of individuals (colleagues, students, etc.)
- Their contribution to the research community
- Their contribution to whole society

Narrative cv x +

→ cienciavita.pt/cv/

^{fct}ciênciavitae published **CIÊNCIAVITAE**

HOME IDENTIFICATION EDUCATION AFFILIATION PROJECTS OUTPUTS ACTIVITIES DISTINCTIONS **NARRATIVE**

NARRATIVE CV

Last updated -

▼ **Identification**

PERSONAL IDENTIFICATION

Full name

Citation name

AUTHOR IDENTIFIERS

Ciência ID

Narrative cv x +

→ cienciavita.pt/cv/

fc **cienciavita** published **CIÊNCIAVITAE**

HOME IDENTIFICATION EDUCATION AFFILIATION PROJECTS OUTPUTS ACTIVITIES DISTINCTIONS **NARRATIVE**

NARRATIVE CV

Last updated -

- ▶ Identification
- ▼ Career profile

Career profile *

4000 characters remaining.

Narrative cv x +

→ ↻ 🏠 cienciavita.pt/cv/

▼ Contributions to science and society

Contributions to the generation of new ideas, tools, methodologies or knowledge *

5000 characters remaining.

Contributions to the development of individuals and/or research teams *

3000 characters remaining.

Contributions to the research community and the broader society *

3000 characters remaining.

Selected outputs and/or activities (up to 5) *

Select publications
related to the project

- ✓ CV highlighting the five most relevant publications
- ✓ Option to include preprints
- ✓ Section encouraging the inclusion of all research outputs (datasets, patents, contributions to norms and standards, etc.)
- ✓ Highlighting knowledge transfer activities aimed at citizens and decision-makers (media appearances, public policy support, outreach activities, organization of public debates, etc.).

European Commission: Open Science Career Assessment Matrix (OS-CAM)

Evaluation of Research Careers fully acknowledging Open Science Practices Rewards, incentives and/or recognition for researchers practicing Open Science.

6 sections, each containing 3 to 5 criteria for evaluating the entire research activity through Open Science:

- Research output
- Research process
- Service and leadership
- Research impact
- Teaching and supervision
- Professional experience

Conclusion

Open science and research evaluation are closely intertwined: open science can lead to new evaluation methods, and evaluation must evolve to take open science into account.

Evaluation should not be limited to “traditional” publications (articles, books, papers), but can/should encompass other scientific outputs: preprints, data, software and source codes, data papers

A wide range of scientific activities can/should be considered in research evaluation: publication, teaching, outreach, peer review, administrative responsibilities, collaborative projects, etc

The framework for changing research evaluation exists, and governments, funders, and institutions are taking up the issue, BUT then it is up to researchers to change practices in the selection or evaluation committees in which they participate!

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CENTRO DE DADOS ABERTOS DE INVESTIGAÇÃO
DA UNIVERSIDADE DO ALGARVE

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